

INTERTEXTUALITY IN LITERARY TEXT

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Annotation: *In Russian linguistics, personal names, set phrases, sentences and texts are fixed as precedent units, familiar to some linguists, stored in their linguistic memory and often used in speech. E. A. Nakhimova evaluates precedent phenomena as a system that has been preserved in the national consciousness of the people. Precedent units in Russian linguistics are studied in biblical texts, myths, folk songs, fairy tales, anecdotes, proverbs, metaphors, phraseology, celebrity names as precedent units. Accordingly, such units as precedent names, precedent sentences and precedent texts are distinguished.*

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In the study of intertextuality by N. Pego-Gros, four precedent units are distinguished: 1. Quote; 2. Help. 3. Extract without quotes. 4. Allusion. The precedent is related to the concept of intertextuality. M. Yuldashev, who studied the linguistic and poetic features of a literary text, describes intertextuality as follows: In some studies, the precedent is noted as a kind of intertextuality. We agree with this. A precedent is one of the manifestations of intertextuality, characterized by the fact that it is well known to the main layers of native speakers and is repeatedly used in speech.⁹¹ Pay attention to the following texts: The air is soft, gentle, as the poet said - "it no longer burns, it only glows." (Erkin Azam. "Writer's" story) The most important thing is the result, the flag belongs to the winner. What is not promised under this flag? Gas will be supplied to a remote mountain village, a smooth asphalt road will be laid across the hills, the salaries of teachers and doctors will be increased several times... a vodka distillery for an uncle, a new shroud for a deceased grandmother... Is it possible not to choose such a wonderfully beautiful vault machine?! (Erkin Azam, "Choose me, choose me..." Journalistic miniature)

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- Jung, G. C. (1968). *The Archetypes and the Collective Unconscious* (2nd ed.). translation by R.F.C. Hull. USA: Prinestone University Press.

In the first of the texts, the phrase “no longer burns, only shines” creates intertextuality. The content of this passage is generally clear to the reader. However, if the reader is familiar with the full text of the extracted poem, he will be able to better understand its content, because the author of the poem is A. Aripov in the following verses through the image of nature to the feelings of a distant youth. It is obvious that he points to:

The sun is shining in the sky
It doesn't burn anymore, it just glows.
Friends, it's already too sunny
This is love left over from a distant youth.
("Autumn landscapes")

Apparently, for a reader who is not familiar with the poem, the verse included in the text gives the impression of a picture of autumn air. The reader who is familiar with the poem will feel that through these verses there is a subtle allusion to the state of mind of the protagonist of the story, which came into his life in the fall. Earlier it was reported that the author (the protagonist of the story) "began to write a book that was born in his heart in the days of disaster." So, although the text “Does not burn, but only glows” used by E. Azamov created intertextuality, only readers who are well acquainted with the poem “Autumn Landscapes” by A. Aripov can understand the purpose for which it is used by the writer.

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